

Gender Mainstreaming Action Plan

Executed by:

UK CEH

Implemented by:

Funded by:

Published by the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH)

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Acknowledgements

Meetings, preparation and publication of this document were kindly supported by contributions from the Global Environment Facility (GEF) through the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) project “Towards Sustainable Phosphorus Cycles in Lake Catchments” (uPcycle) and the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology.

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Key terms and definitions

Gender. Gender refers to the socially constructed roles, behaviours, activities, and attributes that a given society considers appropriate for different genders. It encompasses a wide range of characteristics, including but not limited to biological sex (male, female, intersex), gender identity (one's internal sense of their gender), gender expression (how one presents their gender to others), and social roles and expectations associated with gender.

Gender Equality. This refers to ensuring all genders have equal access to rights and opportunities.

Gender Equity. This describes the process of considering and compensating for differences and disadvantages experienced by different genders to achieve fairness. Gender equity leads to gender equality.

Gender Inclusivity. This refers to ensuring that all genders are included and considered in decision-making processes, policies, programmes, and initiatives. It emphasizes the need to address the needs, priorities, and perspectives of individuals of all genders.

Gender Mainstreaming. This is a strategy for integrating gender perspectives into all stages of policy-making, planning, implementation, and monitoring. It involves analysing the implications of any planned action on different genders and taking proactive steps to promote gender equality and address gender disparities.

1. Introduction

Unsustainable phosphorus use is a global challenge. While phosphorus is an essential component of fertilisers and is critical in meeting global food demands, phosphorus losses from the food system to freshwaters is a major cause of ecosystem damage and biodiversity loss. In addition, climate change may impact both phosphorus pollution and its utility in agricultural systems, placing the issue at the centre of the Triple Planetary Crisis of Climate Change, Pollution, and Biodiversity Loss. In particular, if phosphorus emissions to our lakes are not reduced in the coming years, then the environmental and socio-economic impacts are predicted to be irreversible. There is currently no global policy on sustainable phosphorus use.

This project will bring together global lake management and sustainable phosphorus management communities to deliver ecosystem recovery through phosphorus emissions reductions for the benefit of communities living near lakes and other impacted aquatic ecosystems. This will be achieved through Our Net Zero Phosphorus (P) approach which is a two-tier approach:

1. Towards Net Zero Phosphorus halting increasing present-day emissions trajectories to avoid further ecosystem degradation and then reducing levels of future emissions to deliver ecosystem recovery.
2. Beyond Net Zero Phosphorus accelerating the selection, placement, and implementation of programmes of measures that deliver multiple long-term benefits along the full value chain.

Accordingly, the project will be delivered through five interrelated components as follows:

1. Increasing clarity on global phosphorus emissions, drivers and impacts leading to increased awareness of national, regional, and global scale sector-specific phosphorus emissions reduction opportunities.
2. Increased uptake of an international monitoring and assessment approach for the optimisation of phosphorus emissions reduction programmes leading to increased ambitions on the protection and restoration of lakes and their catchments and associated socio-economic benefits.
3. Improved understanding across government departments and stakeholders in Chile on opportunities for enhancing phosphorus emission reduction programmes and policies, targeting the protection of lake basins and the Humboldt Current Large Marine Ecosystem;
4. Improved national, regional, and global awareness of the benefits of integrating sustainable phosphorus management across existing policies within a coordinated approach (e.g., across World Water Quality Alliance (WWQA) and the Global Programme of Action (GPA); IPBES; IPCC; FAO, etc.)
5. Monitoring and Evaluation.

To date, very few studies have shown the relationship between the phosphorus cycle and gender issues. The project uPcycle will promote Gender Equality throughout its execution. The project will adhere to the GEF's Gender Policy and UNEP's Operational Policy on Gender Equity in Development and Gender Mainstreaming Policy. In addition, the uPcycle project has drafted a Gender Mainstreaming Framework (See Appendix 2) which informs the content of this Gender Mainstreaming Action Plan.

The purpose of this document

This document describes the Gender Mainstreaming Plan for the uPcycle project, outlining the objectives, strategies and monitoring indicators required to integrate gender considerations into the project and associated outputs.

- **Chapter 1** provides an overview of national and international gender commitments, the importance of gender mainstreaming within sustainable phosphorus projects and the Chilean national context relating to gender.
- **Chapter 2** outlines the gender mainstreaming plan.
- **Chapter 3** describes how gender mainstreaming will operationalise the project's Gender mainstreaming Framework.

The document concludes with several appendices and an annexe providing supporting materials for the plan. It is expected that this plan will be used by the relevant project implementing partners to help ensure gender mainstreaming efforts are integrated into their respective project activities and outputs.

Main international and national commitments related to gender equality

The essential role in the provision, management and protection of water played by women, formally appeared in the Third Principle of the Dublin Declaration, outlined during the International Conference on Water and Environment (Dublin, 1992) and endorsed by over 100 countries. The acceptance and implementation of this principle requires policies to (i) address women's specific needs, (ii) to equip and empower women to participate at all levels in water resources programmes, and (iii) to include women in decision-making and implementation, in ways defined by them (United Nations, 1992b).

Since the Dublin Declaration, the role of women in water management for health, nutrition and ecosystem balance has been recognized in several international documents (e.g. Rio Declaration on Environment and Development 1992). These documents reason that women have a vital role in environmental management, and their full participation is, therefore, essential to achieving sustainable development (United Nations, 1992a). In addition, there is international recognition that the

involvement of women and men in decision-making roles at all levels can promote water resources management, and significant opportunities exist to address gender equity through integrated management of water resources (Chancellor F., 2003).

The importance of gender mainstreaming for achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goals has been recognised (UN Women et al., 2024). SDG 5 focussing on Gender Equality seeks to “ensure the full and effective participation of women and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and public life”; and to “undertake reforms to give women equal rights to economic resources, as well as access to ownership and control over land and other forms of property, financial services, inheritance, and natural resources following national laws”(UN Women, 2024b). Even though the role of women has been recognised as fundamental for the sustainable management of the environment and water resources, gender inequities and gaps persist. These gaps are mainly manifested as unequal access to natural resources; unbalanced participation and decision-making in environmental planning and governance at all levels; and uneven access to socio-economic benefits and services (Global Environment Facility, 2017).

To address these gaps the GEF Policy on Gender Equity specifies gender-responsive actions, from design to implementation. In addition, monitoring and evaluation should be designed and implemented to ensure that GEF programmes and projects are not only designed with a good understanding of relevant gender differences, roles and needs. Finally, active pursuit of activities that contribute to equal access to and control over resources and decision making while empowering women and girls are encouraged (Global Environment Facility, 2018).

The importance of gender mainstreaming in sustainable phosphorus management in lake catchments.

Incorporating gender mainstreaming efforts into projects and programmes aims to integrate considerations for genders across different social, economic and geographic demographics in both planning and implementation (Prasetyo et al., 2023). Acknowledging the importance of gender equality and women's rights in sustainable phosphorus management is crucial from a human rights standpoint (Agarwal, 2018). Furthermore, research indicates that initiatives aiming to achieve more sustainable use of agricultural nutrients will achieve greater efficiency and efficacy by considering gender equality and incorporating gender equity measures. This integration has the potential to benefit various areas such as food security, water security, and sustainable agriculture ((Adam et al., 2021; Farnworth et al., 2017; Leslie et al., 2019; Meinzen-Dick et al., 2014).

Men and women possess distinct priorities and requirements concerning the ecosystem services offered by lakes and their catchment areas depending on welfare considerations and cultural norms. Food value chains include agriculture and aquaculture sectors which are key to driving phosphorus cycles. Whilst there is limited high-quality gender-disaggregated data regarding value chains, it is acknowledged that gender equality in many of the key sectors involved in the food value chain has not been achieved. Ensuring gender equality in the value chains driving global, regional, and national phosphorus cycles is an important step in achieving inclusive sustainable phosphorus economies.

Implementing a gender-responsive and socially inclusive approach should expand the scope of any project. In doing so, practitioners will benefit from a broader knowledge base and will increase the equity of benefits from their actions (Broeckhoven & Cliquet, 2015). Integration of gender considerations tends to generate broader local buy-in and can incentivise both women and men to contribute to restoration efforts, providing greater opportunities for enhanced well-being for women and men alike, as well as chances for the long-term sustainability of freshwater restoration efforts (Ahmed, 2005)(Ahmed, 2005).

Failing to engage with women or acknowledge their contributions to the subject area carries inherent risks to the efficacy of a project (Sinharoy & Caruso, 2019)(Sinharoy & Caruso, 2019). Initiatives in aquatic resources management that overlook gender considerations have worsened gender disparities and, in some cases, restricted women's access to water and resources, diminished their influence and autonomy, and increased their workload (Ahmed, 2005; Freitas et al., 2020)(Ahmed, 2005; Freitas et al., 2020). Gender equality must, therefore, be a central consideration when developing an internationally accepted framework and monitoring and assessment approach to inform the development and implementation of sustainable phosphorus management programmes in lake catchments. The uPcycle project will use gender-sensitive indicators in the framework to assess gender bias.

The uPcycle project will investigate the availability of data on the role of women in the key activities identified, in particular in the Demo Component 3 with a focus in Chile

Chile

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Mandates and frameworks on gender

Chile has ratified all the substantial international treaties on Human Rights (GOV.UK, 2023). In 1991 the National Women’s Service was created to promote public policies for gender equality. Since 2015 the Ministry of Women and Gender Equality (Law 20820 of 03/08/15) was established to design, coordinate, and evaluate policies, plans and programmes aimed at promoting gender equality and seeking the elimination of all forms of arbitrary discrimination against women (Chilean Ministry of Women and Gender Equality, 2024). Several laws seek to promote gender equality in Chile, these are described in table 1. below.

Laws that promote gender equality in Chile

Law 21643 - Modifies the labor code and other legal bodies, regarding the prevention, investigation and sanction of workplace, sexual harassment or violence at work. January 15, 2024.	Law 20.348, which protects the right to equal remuneration between women and men, June 19, 2009.
Law 21.370 Modifies the General Law on Fisheries and Aquaculture to promote gender equity in the fisheries and aquaculture sector, 2021.	Law 20,399, which grants the worker the right to a nursery, November 23, 2009.
Law 20.609, which establishes measures against discrimination, July 24, 2012.	Law 20,255, which establishes the pension reform and granted women a bonus for daughters and sons born alive, March 17, 2008.
Law 20.595, creates the Ethical Family Income for families in extreme poverty and the employment subsidy for women, May 17, 2012.	Law 20,166, which extends the right of working mothers to breastfeed their children even when there is no nursery, February 12, 2007.
Law 20.545, which modifies the maternity protection regulations and incorporates paternal postnatal leave, October 17, 2011.	Law 20,066, on Domestic Violence, October 7, 2005.
Law 20.507, which defines the crime of trafficking and establishes rules for its prevention and more effective criminal prosecution, April 8, 2011.	Law 20,005, which typifies and punishes sexual harassment, March 18, 2005.
Law 20.480, which modifies the Penal Code and the Law on Intrafamily Violence, December 18, 2010.	Article 95 bis of the Labor Code that establishes a nursery for seasonal workers, modified on January 16, 2003.
Article 59.- Added to the first paragraph of article 2 of Law No. 20609, which establishes measures against discrimination, after the word “sex,” the expression “gender,” July 24, 2012	Law 19,591, which modifies the labor code regarding maternity protection, November 9, 1998.
Law 20.418, which sets standards on information, guidance and benefits in fertility regulation, published January 28, 2010.	Article 59.- Added to the first paragraph of article 2 of Law No. 20609, which establishes measures against discrimination, after the word “sex,” the expression “gender,” Published July 24, 2012

Table 1. – Laws that promote gender equality in Chile. Source: Ministerio del Medio ambiente Chile. 2020. Informe del Estado del Medio Ambiente 2020 (IEMA) & Ministerio de la Mujer y la Equidad de Género. (2024). *Legislative Advances – Published Laws. Ministerio de La Mujer y La Equidad de Género.* https://minmujeryeg.gob.cl/?page_id=35959.

The Report on the State of the Environment (2020) shows Chile's progress in achieving gender equity and stresses the main challenges which are related to information gaps and inconsistency in the inclusion of gender as listed below (Chilean Ministry of Environment, 2021).

Need for gender-disaggregated information: The absence of gender-disaggregated information makes the analysis of the environment biased and partial, which makes it necessary to establish baselines, monitor progress, and evaluate the results in an exhaustive and effective manner.

Inequality and gaps in gender inclusion: This causes low coherence and less efficiency in the application of policies and programmes.

In recent years, a variety of initiatives have been developed in Chile to promote gender equality and strengthen women's autonomy (Investors For Equality, 2021). For example:

- The **gender strategy** of the Economic Development Agency (CORFO) – this guides, monitors, and evaluates the strategies to include the gender perspective in its activities, in coordination with the National Service for Women and Gender Equity, and the Gender Unit of the Ministry of Economy (Chilean Economic Development Agency, 2024).
- Development of **gender statistics** by the National Statistics Institute (INE) - this aims to visualize and understand the gaps, barriers and inequities between men and women. As well as the production of the **gender atlas**, a collection of maps that, through indicators at the regional level, show gender inequities, gaps or visible barriers between genders (Instituto Nacional de Estadísticas (INE), 2024a).
- The **Win-Win: Gender Equality Means Good Business**- this is funded by the European Union (EU) Partnership Instrument and implemented by UN Women in partnership with the International Labor Organization (ILO) to promote gender equality through the private sector (Win-Win, 2021).

National context in relation to gender equality and women's empowerment

The Human Development Index (IDH) for Chile in 2021 was 0.855, positioning the country in the “very high” human development category, the highest of the Latin America and the Caribbean region. However, work still needs to be done in Chile to achieve gender equality. The Global Gender Gap Index of the World Economic Forum assigns Chile an index of 0.781 for the year 2024, ranking 21st out of 146 countries (World Economic Forum, 2024). Although there has been progress in terms of gender equality in recent years, the goals to close the gap between men and women in economic participation and opportunity (0.662) and political empowerment (0.502) have not yet been achieved (ibid.).

As of February 2021, only 22.6% of seats in parliament were held by women. In 2018, 5.8% of women aged 15-49 years reported that they had been subject to physical and/or sexual violence by a

current or former intimate partner in the previous 12 months (UN Women, 2024a).

As of December 2020, only 50.8% of indicators needed to monitor the SDGs from a gender perspective were available, with gaps in key areas. In particular, data were sparse on key labour market indicators such as the gender pay gap. In addition, many areas – such as gender and poverty, physical and sexual harassment, women’s access to assets (including land), and gender and the environment – lack comparable methodologies for regular monitoring (UN Women, 2024a).

According to estimates of the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC), women’s participation in work due to the effect of COVID-19 in Chile has been affected more than men. Following the pandemic, the average participation of women in work is 46%, below the Latin American average (59%). This may be related to the unequal distribution of time devoted by women to care tasks compared with men, a situation intensified during COVID-19.

Reports on economic autonomy in 2021 also show gender disparities. In Chile, 9% of the women are in a situation of poverty compared with 8.2% of men. According to the World Bank, only 29.6% of companies in Chile include participation from women in their ownership models. In the case of women, the distribution of low-income workers is approximately 1.6 times greater than that of men. The earnings gap between male and female employees is larger in Chile than in other countries. The average salary of full-time male employees is 12% higher than that of their female counterparts (OECD, 2021). In rural environments, these gender gaps can be even more pronounced with diminished contribution to decision-making (Agholor, 2019).

Artisanal fishing has been defined and regulated as an extractive subsector where women have been excluded. To advance gender equity in the sector, in 2021 Law No. 21.370 was approved, which establishes equity criteria in the integration of fishing and aquaculture organizations and recognizes traditional or ancestral trades that women perform in the coves (Industrias Pesqueras, 2021).

According to CASEN (2015) 9% of the national population identifies themselves as indigenous. Of that percentage, 83.8% identify themselves as Mapuches. In the case of the communes located within the Villarrica Lake Basin, the commune of Curarrehue has a 66.4% indigenous population, Villarrica has 27.1% and Pucón 27.9% (Instituto Nacional de Estadísticas (INE), 2024b). This is relevant for the development of the uPcycle Project because the gender relations in Mapuche society and Chilean society are not the same and the discrimination towards Mapuche women is different from the discrimination experienced by non-Mapuche women (Richards, 2003). At the same time, the indigenous population have higher rates of multidimensional poverty than the non-indigenous population (CASEN, 2015) (Mesa De Mujeres Rurales, 2022).

2. The uPcycle Gender Mainstreaming Plan

The uPcycle Gender Mainstreaming Plan

This Gender Mainstreaming Plan aims to ensure the integration of gender considerations throughout the project’s activities. The primary objectives of the plan are to:

1. To achieve gender inclusive representation in sustainable phosphorus management initiatives by providing equal opportunities for women, girls, local communities, and marginalised groups to participate in and benefit from project activities.
2. Enhance women’s participation and role in decision-making processes.
3. Provide equitable access to capacity building and knowledge sharing across all stakeholder groups.
4. 4. Contribute to long-term change by ensuring project outputs address gender inequities and raise awareness of the importance on integrating gender considerations into sustainable phosphorus initiatives

These objectives and their associated strategies and indicators are presented in Figure 1.

	REACH	BENEFIT	EMPOWER	TRANSFORM
OBJECTIVE	To achieve gender inclusive representation in sustainable phosphorus management initiatives.	Provide equitable access to capacity building and knowledge sharing across all stakeholder groups.	Enhance women’s participation and role in decision-making processes	Contribute to long-term change by ensuring project outputs address gender inequities and raising awareness of the importance on considering gender in sustainable phosphorus initiatives.
STRATEGY	Mitigate barriers to women and members of minority groups participating in workshops and pre-establish gender representation objectives by integrating gender mainstreaming objectives into the results framework	Consider gender differences and needs when planning workshops or training opportunities. Strive for gender equity by addressing and compensating for gendered disadvantages.	Addressing gender gaps in decision-making, leadership and management roles. Encouraging and reinforcing women’s agency in these roles as well as in community spaces.	Improve internal and external understanding of the intricacies and importance of gender considerations by raising awareness and providing training opportunities.
INDICATORS	Percentage of different genders of different age-groups and ethnicities participating in a project workshop, meeting or field visit. Figures will be established from participants’ self-report and will be evaluated throughout the project lifecycle.	Gender-disaggregated data collected on workshop and training outcomes and attendance (e.g. increased confidence and skills gained).	Decisions made and responsibilities demonstrated by women throughout the project. Gender representation in decision making roles and working groups.	A shift in attitudes and an enhanced effort placed on implementing gender mainstreaming demonstrated in future project planning.

Figure 1. uPcycle project’s structured indicator framework for gender mainstreaming.

Gender integration across the project

The project objective is to deliver a Framework on phosphorus emissions reductions from land to water to improve the protection and restoration of freshwater and coastal ecosystems, with demonstration in Chile. Activities in the project will be guided by a gender-responsive approach.

The following principles will be followed throughout the project:

- Structure inclusive and gender-sensitive project teams with technical skills and experience to support gender-sensitive actions. The Project Coordination Unit will receive gender training and will seek assistance from an external gender specialist where necessary.
- Ensure the equal voice and influence of women and men in all aspects of the project, using culturally sensitive and appropriate approaches.
- Ensure that women and women's organisations are represented in any stakeholder consultations or working groups (e.g. component 1: cross-sector working group; Component 2: global community of practice on sustainable lake management).
- Ensure that the roles, needs, abilities and vulnerabilities of women and men are equally recognised (all components).
- Promote equal rights to access and benefit from the sustainable phosphorus management framework in Chile (component 3).
- Support the full, equal, and effective participation of women and men in decision-making and all actions related to the development, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of the project.
- Ensure that all knowledge management activities both face-to-face and virtual, are accessible to women, taking into account location, time, transportation constraints, household responsibilities, computer access, telephones and internet, language, etc., which may affect ability to attend/participate in project activities.

More details on gender mainstreaming indicators within the project results framework are shown (Appendix 1).

Monitoring and evaluation of gender-responsive activities

Throughout all uPcycle Project components the gender mainstreaming strategies will be monitored regularly to evaluate if the desired outcomes are being achieved, and to determine whether adaptive mechanisms need to be developed if outcomes are not being reached. The Gender Mainstreaming Plan presents a clear vision of desired gender impacts and targets, which is fully aligned with the project results framework and GEF/UNEP Policies.

Gender-sensitive monitoring and evaluation reports, including project progress reports, mid-term evaluations, and terminal evaluations will be developed.

3. Operationalising the Gender Mainstreaming Framework

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Gender Mainstreaming Framework Considerations

To ensure effective integration of gender considerations into the uPcycle Project, this gender mainstreaming plan has been informed by the project's Gender Mainstreaming Framework which is intended to be published during the project's lifecycle (see Appendix 2.). The purpose of the uPcycle Gender Mainstreaming Framework is to serve as a resource for stakeholders involved in projects and programmes aimed at achieving sustainable phosphorus cycles in lake catchments, whether at the national or subnational level. This resource outlines the steps required to integrate gender mainstreaming efforts throughout the lifecycle of a project or programme.

This gender plan has used the Gender Mainstreaming Framework's enclosed checklist to ensure effective gender mainstreaming throughout the project. The associated considerations are listed below.

Articulating the project's specific objectives and targets and the importance of incorporating gender considerations within the project

This gender mainstreaming plan, including the objectives and indicators included in the results framework, (See Appendix 1.) clearly articulates the gender mainstreaming targets for the project. These will continually be highlighted to component leads and will be regularly monitored using predefined indicators. For example, gender representation targets for project workshops (e.g. output 1.2.2.) will be assessed by participant's self-report data and will be included in the workshops' reports.

Governance structure and quality assessment established for the gender mainstreaming component of the project/programme

The PCU is responsible for governing the implementation and monitoring of gender mainstreaming throughout the project lifecycle.

The Assistant Project Coordinator will lead the coordination of the gender mainstreaming plan for the project, as such, the project will not be employing a separate 'gender expert'. This is justified by the need to have continual gender-responsive efforts throughout the lifetime of the project. uPcycle values the opportunity to ensure 'in house' gender equality skills are built across the PCU, whilst acknowledging the opportunity to seek external expertise at a later point the project.

The Project Coordinator and Assistant Project Coordinator participated in multiple training webinars and courses (incl. UN CC:E-Learn Course 'Open Online Course on Gender and Environment'). This was to aid in developing the gender mainstreaming plan for the project and to support the team in fulfilling associated deliverables.

Qualitative and quantitative data to be collected

In addition to quantitative indicators (see Appendix 1.), qualitative gender-disaggregated data will also be sought after and considered when incorporating gender considerations into the project framework and associated recommendations. This may inform efforts to compensate for gender inequities when planning project activities i.e. considering gender roles and disadvantages when designing workshops to ensure women feel empowered and have inclusive avenues through which to contribute.

Efforts made to fully involve women throughout the different facets of the project/programme to enhance their capacity

Gender representation amongst the governing groups within the project has been heavily considered with a particular focus on empowering women to take on decision-making roles. Additionally, stakeholder groups and the community of practice (outputs 1.2.1 & 2.1.1) have quantitative objectives of achieving at least 30% representation of women. Additionally, workshops and training events also have gender representation objectives (see Appendix 1.).

Minimising reporting burdens

Monitoring gender mainstreaming efforts relies on participants and stakeholders to self-report personal information such as gender, ethnicity, age group etc. so that an intersectional view of the gender representation can be reported on. To comprehensively report on the intersections of gender would require many topics to be reported on such as educational background, geography and household income to name a few. The number of demographic questions that participants will be asked has been reduced to five in the interest of reducing the reporting burden, mitigating attrition at the self-report stage and maintaining an ethical protocol by minimising requests for sensitive information. The questions included in the demographic self-report survey can be found in Appendix 3.

Ethical considerations for gender reporting

Ethics approval was sought after and granted by the UKCEH Research Ethics Committee on 11th March 2024 prior to the collection of any personal data.

Transparency with communicating results and dissemination of lessons learned from monitoring gender mainstreaming efforts

A project gender report is intended to be published on the uPcycle website during the project's life-cycle. This will present anonymised gender representation figures and findings from the monitoring of the gender mainstreaming of the project. uPcycle will also publish the Gender Mainstreaming Framework in addition to having ambitions of further exploring opportunities to disseminate outputs exploring the relationship between gender and phosphorus.

Utilising gender mainstreaming monitoring results to adapt management and improve implementation?

The gender mainstreaming efforts of the project will be regularly reviewed by the PCU to assess efficacy and identify required actions or considerations. Necessary improvements will be made to ensure the gender mainstreaming plan is effectively implemented and objectives are achieved.

Has the broader enabling environment been considered?

Political Support has been established through the project's partnership with the Chilean Ministry of Environment and will support the project's efforts to achieve equitable benefits for all stakeholders.

Raising awareness about gender considerations internally as well as externally?

The project's dissemination of the Gender Mainstreaming Framework aims to raise awareness of the importance of integrating gender considerations as well as providing a resource to aid the implementation of gender mainstreaming efforts into existing and pending projects and programmes on sustainable phosphorus management in lake catchments. Additionally, to foster internal awareness raising, external expertise may be considered later in the project's lifecycle for the purpose of providing focused workshops on gender equality and social inclusivity.

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5. Appendices

Appendix 1. Gender mainstreaming measures and indicators throughout the Project results framework.

Output	Project Activities	Action	Indicators & Targets
<p>Component 1: Increasing clarity on global phosphorus emissions, drivers and impacts leading to increased awareness of national, regional, and global scale sector-specific phosphorus emissions reduction opportunities</p> <p>Outcome 1: Global stakeholders have the evidence needed to assess the capacity for phosphorus emissions reductions to contribute to their commitments to delivering large-scale ecosystem restoration ambitions (e.g., the UN Decade and SDGs). Improved international and cross-sector awareness of the need for coordinated action to deliver large-scale phosphorus emissions reduction.</p>			
<p>Output 1.1 The global phosphorus emissions dashboard beta version was developed and implemented as a publicly available online mapping tool allowing visualization of emissions estimates and their contribution to eutrophication risk across the world's large lakes, extending to coastal waters.</p>	<p>1.1.1 Establish a global phosphorus emissions assessment group, bringing together data providers with which the global extent of emissions and their impacts on freshwater and coastal ecosystems can be mapped.</p>	<p>Identify women representatives as data providers.</p>	<p>Indicator: Percentage of women per peer reference group</p> <p>Target: At least 30%</p>
	<p>1.1.2 Produce the global phosphorus emissions dashboard - building on existing web-based infrastructure to host and integrate relevant global data streams.</p>	<p>Women's organizations and gender specialists are part of the group that validates the beta version of the dashboard.</p>	<p>Indicator: Percentage of women per peer reference group</p> <p>Target: At least 30%</p>

Output	Project Activities	Action	Indicators & Targets
Output 1.2 Two global stakeholder workshops demonstrate the Dashboard and inform discussions on cross-sectoral drivers of global phosphorus emissions to freshwater and coastal ecosystems, as well as opportunities to address them.	1.2.1 Establish a cross-sector working group with participation across relevant global policy sectors and International Industry Associations, representing a ‘community of influence’ across key emissions sectors (including agriculture, food waste, aquaculture, wastewater, and nutrient recycling sectors).	Engage targeted women representatives to participate in the cross-sector working group.	Indicator: Percentage of women per peer reference group Target: At least 30%
	1.2.2 Hold two workshops to showcase, and further develop, the global phosphorus emissions dashboard and explore cross-country-sector influences on the anthropogenic phosphorus cycle impacting on exemplar national or basin-scale phosphorus emissions programs	Ensure equal participation of women and men at the workshops.	Indicator: Percentage of women/men Target: 50% of stakeholders actively participating in workshops are women
Output 1.3 A White Paper outlining priority sector-specific actions towards delivering a more sustainable global anthropogenic phosphorus cycle to support improved food security while delivering on global ecosystem protection and restoration ambitions.	1.3.1 Produce recommendations for global actions outlining the benefits of ‘Future World’ policy development options and their capacity to deliver change against ‘Present Day’ conditions within the context of existing relevant national and international public and private policy frameworks	Revision of the ‘White Paper’ by gender specialist to ensure that gender considerations have been included.	Indicator: A gender-responsive ‘White Paper’ Target: 1 gender-responsive ‘White Paper’

Output	Project Activities	Action	Indicators & Targets
Component 2: Building the Global Net Zero Phosphorus Community of Practice on sustainable phosphorus management in lake basins, producing the uPcycle Framework and Assessment Approach and accelerating its uptake to optimise emissions reduction programs.			

Output	Project Activities	Action	Indicators & Targets
Outcome 2: Increased uptake of an international monitoring and assessment approach for the optimization of phosphorus emissions reduction programs leading to increased ambitions on the protection and restoration of lakes and their catchments and associated socio-economic benefits.			
Output 2.1 Convene the Global Community of Practice on Sustainable Phosphorus Management in Lake Basins; a global network of practitioners tasked with assessing the global baseline on large-scale phosphorus emission reduction programs.	2.1.1 Establish a Global Community of Practice on Sustainable Phosphorus Management - to co-develop the uPcycle Framework providing stakeholders and practitioners with a conceptual model, centred on the Net Zero Phosphorus concept.	Engage targeted women representatives to participate in the Net Zero P Lake Network.	Indicator: Percentage of women per peer reference group Target: At least 30%
	2.2.1 Develop the uPcycle framework - setting out the multiple benefits of implementing sustainable phosphorus management plans to protect and restore lake basins whilst releasing multiple socio-economic benefits	Socioeconomic indicators identified in the uPcycle framework are gender-sensitive. A gender specialist participates in the development group.	Indicator: Gender-sensitive indicators are identified. Target: At least 1 indicator is gender-sensitive
	2.2.2 Develop the monitoring and assessment approach - to allow lake basin managers to conduct internationally coordinated assessments of the operational effectiveness of existing programs whilst identifying opportunities to improve them		
Output 2.2 Guidance materials leading to the international implementation of the uPcycle net zero phosphorus framework and monitoring and assessment Approach, co-developed with the Global Community of Practice.	2.2.3 Hold knowledge exchange workshops to disseminate guidance materials and common assessment methodology to the Community of Practice	Ensure equal participation of women and men at the workshops.	Indicator: Percentage of women/men Target: 50% of stakeholders actively participating in workshops are women

Output	Project Activities	Action	Indicators & Targets
<p>Output 2.3</p> <p>Global baseline assessment report produced and shared with countries showcasing the first internationally coordinated assessment of present-day phosphorus emissions programs for lakes and increasing international motivation to implement new policies, programs, and/or investments leading to more sustainable phosphorus management.</p>	<p>2.3.1 Hold an open seminar series providing the opportunity for practitioners to introduce their emissions reduction programs in detail in the context of the uPcycle Framework, highlighting specific challenges and solutions, with opportunities to learn from the experiences of others.</p>	<p>Ensure equal participation of women and men in the open seminar series.</p>	<p>Indicator: Percentage of women per peer reference group</p> <p>Target: At least 30%</p>
	<p>2.3.2 Synthesize the global baseline - A globally coordinated assessment of emissions reduction programs to produce a report documenting the current levels of disparity in approaches and barriers to their effective implementation.</p>		
	<p>2.3.3 Field visits to showcase exemplars of effective sustainable phosphorus management in established programs</p>		

Output	Project Activities	Action	Indicators & Targets
<p>Component 3: Demonstrating the uPcycle Monitoring and Assessment Approach in Chile from basin to transboundary scales, in the context of enhancing existing policies.</p>			
<p>Outcome 3: Improved understanding across Chilean government departments and its stakeholders on opportunities for enhancing phosphorus emission reduction programs and policies, targeting the protection of lake basins and the Humboldt Current Large Marine Ecosystem.</p>			

Output	Project Activities	Action	Indicators & Targets
<p>Output 3.1 Produce a virtual surveillance portal integrating data streams to produce baseline and forecast outputs on phosphorus emissions and their impacts on the Lake Villarrica Basin, to inform the development of a national scale system.</p>	<p>3.1.1 Produce a virtual environment capable of assessing phosphorus emission reduction scenarios, impacts and benefits to inform stakeholder engagement and policy development - e.g. a virtual surveillance portal.</p>	<p>Guarantee gender-inclusive approaches and language in the virtual surveillance portal. A gender specialist participates in the development group.</p>	<p>Indicator: A gender-responsive virtual surveillance portal</p> <p>Target: 1 gender-responsive virtual surveillance portal</p>
	<p>3.1.2 Provide training in the application of novel monitoring and modelling approaches and in data interrogation and visualization techniques delivered through staff exchanges and directed training activities, drawing on the expertise of the UKCEH and relevant national and international partners.</p>	<p>Ensure equal participation of women and men at the training workshops.</p>	<p>Indicator: Percentage of women/men</p> <p>Target: At least 50% of staff exchanges are women</p>
<p>Output 3.2 Two virtual laboratory workshops and targeted awareness-raising materials to engage stakeholders in the co-development and uptake of new opportunities for sector-specific emissions reductions at the lake basin- to national scales in Chile, utilizing the surveillance portal.</p>	<p>3.2.1 Hold two virtual laboratory workshops - to develop and showcase the surveillance portal and identify synergies and opportunities to release multiple benefits through more sustainable phosphorus management across the value chain.</p>	<p>Ensure equal participation of women and men at the training workshops.</p>	<p>Indicator: Percentage of women/men</p> <p>Target: At least 50% of workshop participants attending the virtual workshop are women.</p>
	<p>3.2.2 Produce targeted awareness-raising materials to engage stakeholders in the co-development and uptake of new opportunities for sector-specific emissions reductions at the lake basin- to national scales in Chile, utilizing the surveillance portal</p>	<p>Review and mainstream gender considerations in awareness-raising materials.</p>	<p>Indicator: # gender-responsive awareness materials</p> <p>Target: At least 3 gender-responsive awareness materials</p>

Output	Project Activities	Action	Indicators & Targets
<p>Output 3.3 A transition plan for Chile is published and shared across relevant government departments identifying opportunities to strengthen the implementation of the existing Lake Villarrica Basin Decontamination Plan, as well as improving the integration of sustainable phosphorus management across national policies for the protection and restoration of lakes and coastal ecosystems.</p>	3.3.1 Compile and review evidence to ‘produce a technical report to support the Lake Villarica decontamination plan approval.	Guarantee gender-inclusive approaches and language in the virtual surveillance portal. A gender specialist participates in the development group.	<p>Indicator: # gender responsive assessment reports</p> <p>Target: 1 gender responsive assessment reports</p>
	3.3.2 Hold quarterly virtual workshops (and ad hoc site visits) to co-develop recommendations for enhancing existing emissions reductions programs within the uPcycle Framework.	Ensure equal participation of women and men at the workshops.	<p>Indicator: Percentage of women/men</p> <p>Target: At least 50% of workshop participants are women</p>
	3.3.3 Publish a transition plan for Chile and disseminate across relevant government bodies	Review and mainstream gender considerations in the transition plan.	<p>Indicator: # gender-responsive transition plan</p> <p>Target: 1 gender-responsive transition plan</p>

Output	Project Activities	Action	Indicators & Targets
<p>Component 4: Accelerate integration of global sustainable phosphorus management opportunities across existing national, regional and global policy frameworks.</p> <p>Outcome 4: Improved national, regional, and global awareness of the benefits of integrating sustainable phosphorus management across existing policies within a coordinated approach (e.g., across World Water Quality Alliance (WWQA) and the Global Programme of Action (GPA); IPBES; IPCC; FAO, etc.).</p>			

<p>Output 4.1 Documented project results disseminated through IW:LEARN activities (1% of the project budget) and established global initiatives.</p>	4.1.1 Establish a project website	<p>Ensure that the work related to gender equality and women's empowerment conducted by the project is showcased in the materials to share on the website, regional and international meetings, etc.</p>	<p>Indicator: Gender content is included in the website, presentations, and reports.</p> <p>Target: At least one presentation, five videos and 1 briefing note including reference to the work related to gender equality and women's empowerment</p>
	4.1.2 Participate with the IW Conference		
	4.1.3 Produce annual update reports		
<p>Output 4.2 Global communications plan to raise awareness across public, private and policy audiences, disseminated to IW:LEARN and established global initiatives.</p>	4.2.1 Conduct a media campaign (e.g., websites, web pages on government sites, and a project portal) to increase public awareness through targeted social media activities, for example, including through the GEF and UNEP social media outlets, including short videos, webinars, surveys, and other interactive communication tools.	<p>Ensure that the media campaign is gender responsive</p>	<p>Indicator: # gender-responsive awareness materials</p> <p>Target: At least 3 gender-responsive comms materials</p>
<p>Output 4.3 The uPcycle Innovation Hub - a web-based information portal to accelerate the development and implementation of sustainable phosphorus initiatives.</p>	4.3.1 Establish the uPcycle innovation hub - providing access to project outputs designed to accelerate the development and implementation of sustainable phosphorus initiatives	<p>Ensure equal participation of women and men in the uPcycle innovation hub</p>	<p>Indicator: Proportion of women and men who participated in Hub</p> <p>Target: At least 30% women and at least 30% men.</p>
<p>Output 4.4 Publish and disseminate Global Policy Briefs to increase awareness across governments on the need for better integration of phosphorus sustainability across the existing policy arena.</p>	4.4.1 Publish and disseminate policy briefs based on the more substantive Global Sustainable Phosphorus Strategy to highlight the ecosystem health and economic case for global action towards improved phosphorus sustainability governance.	<p>Ensure both men and women receive and have access to the policy briefs</p>	<p>Indicator: Global Policy Briefs are widely disseminated to both men and women.</p>

Appendix 2. uPcycle Gender Mainstreaming Framework draft

<https://www.upcyclelakes.org/s/Gender-Mainstreaming-Framework.pdf>

Appendix 3. Demographic self-report survey

<https://www.upcyclelakes.org/s/uPcycle-Gender-and-Demographic-Self-Report-Survey.pdf>

6. Annexe:

Table 1: Relevant organizations working with gender issues in Chile

The table below presents relevant institutions and organizations *inter alia* that work with gender issues in Chile.

Name	Description
ANAMURI	The National Association of Rural and Indigenous Women (ANAMURI) is a Chilean non-profit and autonomous civil organization integrated by women, whose mission is to organize and promote the development of rural and indigenous women in Chile.
Centro de Estudios para el Desarrollo de la Mujer (CEDEM)	The organization contributes to strengthening democracy, overcoming social exclusion and transforming gender relations, generating knowledge, participating in critical debate and promoting active citizenship.
Centro de Estudios de la Mujer (CEM)	CEM promotes the transfer of gender knowledge to different social and professional groups to ensure greater competence in their work.
Comunidad Mujer	A civil society organization that has been promoting, for 20 years, social, cultural, normative, and organizational transformation for gender equality in Chile.
Corporación de Mujeres de la Pesca Artesanal	The Corporation of Women of Artisanal Fishing in Chile seeks to make visible and strengthen women in the fishing sector -whether they are shuckers, netters, fisherwomen, seaweed, or shellfish collectors- for gender equality.

Name	Description
Fundación Chile Mujeres	A non-profit organization was born in 2015 to promote legal and cultural changes necessary to promote equal rights and job opportunities for women in Chile.
Fundación Instituto de la mujer	Produces, systematizes, and disseminates knowledge through studies, workshops, and seminars, seeking consensus points with other civil society stakeholders to influence policies.
Observatorio de Género y Equidad	It articulates women's organizations to facilitate public debate and citizen control over equality policies.
Fundación PRODEMU	Is the first State Institution that takes charge of the needs, requirements and demands of women in Chile, to facilitate women participation, organization and comprehensive development, promoting their empowerment and encouraging them to achieve a better quality of life.